

The Framework Model for the Promotion of Education about Standardisation in Line with EU Values and Interests

Vladislav V. Fomin

Vilnius University
and
Interdisciplinary
Transformation
University (IT:U)
Austria

vfomin@gmail.com

Nizar Abdelkafi

Politecnico di Milano

nizar.abdelkafi@polimi.it

Knut Blind

Fraunhofer
Institute for
Systems and
Innovation
Research
and
TU Berlin

knut.blind@tu-berlin.de

Rimvydas Laužikas

Vilnius University

rimvydas.lauzikas@kf.vu.lt

Abstract

The European Union's strategic vision on standardisation has evolved beyond its traditional role of ensuring technical compatibility, safety, and efficiency. The 2022 EU Standardisation Strategy emphasizes the importance of integrating fundamental rights, European values, and societal priorities into the standardisation process. This shift aligns with broader EU objectives to enhance global competitiveness, economic resilience, and open strategic autonomy. At the same time, the existing frameworks for education about standardisation do not consider these aspects desired by EU policy. More to the problem, educational efforts around standardisation in Europe are rather disparate, artisan and professor-centric. There is no common framework detailing the type of knowledge and competences that students should develop in standardisation. Given this background, the promotion of the new policy imperatives into education requires a systemic approach, which caters for the new strategic orientation of education about standardisation and helps to overcome the disparities of the educational landscape. Building on the Desing Science Research Methodology (DSRM), this paper proposes a hierarchical framework model of an Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS) to facilitate the reinvigoration of education about standardisation in Europe. The developed Framework Model of ITCoS (FM ITCoS) views the higher education (HE) system as a hierarchy of functional levels, starting from the strategic orientation of HE at the top of the model, curricula development and integration tasks in the middle, and technical aids and tools for implementation of teaching activities at the bottom of the model. The paper ends with discussion on extant and new roles of standardisation professionals, and how the FM-ITCoS can drive the education about standardisation to the policy-desired objectives.

Keywords: Education; Standardisation, Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS), hierarchical framework model, Desing Science Research Methodology (DSRM).

1 Introduction

In recent years, there has been an important shift in the EU's strategic vision on standardisation. While the traditional role of standardisation has been to provide various technical solutions, ensuring safety, quality, compatibility, and efficiency across a multitude of different domains,